

Drug Action and Brain Ribonucleoproteins*

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For this afternoon's lecture, I have decided the topic on "Drug action and brain ribonucleoproteins"—it is a study, where emphasis has been made on both structure and function in a well-defined biological system.

For a number of years, the work of our laboratory has been focussed on the action of different convulsant and tranquilizer group of drugs at the level of ribonucleoprotein constituents of brain tissues studied biochemically and by histochemical procedure. It has been suggested that the fundamental action of a drug might be explained not only by its ability to react with or in some way influence the normal function of an enzyme or enzyme system but also on the basis of its action towards some of the important structural and functional components of the cell.

Our interest in the ribonucleoprotein as the site of neuropharmacologic drug action arose out of the following lines of thought and development in this field :

- (a) during increased functional activity, stimulation or stress, there are significant histological changes in the size, distribution and organization of the cytoplasmic basophilic materials of nerve cell bodies ;
- (b) the probable role of RNA and RNP in different functional systems of brain. The functional aspects of nerve cell ribosomes are important because of an apparently high turnover of proteins and ribonucleic acids in the central nervous system ;
- (c) several investigators have suggested from their studies, in the last few years, that there is a possible connection between the changes in the functional activity of brain and the qualitative and/or quantitative changes in the RNA constituents of brain tissue. Hydén and co-workers¹, using much more elegant techniques, have demonstrated that total neuronal RNA and protein are increased with various kinds of stimulation. These investigators² have also observed more extensive changes, both qualitative and quantitative, at the level of neuronal and glial RNA constituents.

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1. H. Hydén and E. Egyhazi, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 1963, 49, 620.
2. E. Egyhazi and H. Hydén, *J. Biophys. Biochem. Cytol.*, 1961, 10, 403.

after the administration of chemical agents and certain neuropharmacologic drugs. Tricyanoaminopropene injection to rabbits caused a significant increase in neuronal RNA with concomitant decrease in the glial RNA and the animals performed significantly better than the controls in avoidance responses³. Tofranil (imipramine), the well-known anti-depressant drug, also produced similar changes, both quantitative and qualitative, in the cytoplasmic and nuclear RNA's of neuronal and glial cells⁴. Geiger⁵ also reported changes in the base composition of RNA of cat brain after metrazol convulsions. The adenine and guanine content of the nucleic acid increased and that of uridine and cytidine content decreased immediately after stimulation. Of equal importance in this context are the observations based on the use of drugs which are known to interfere with RNA and protein biosynthesis and functional changes brought about in brain. Dingman and Sporn⁶ showed by elaborate maze trial experimentation that intracisternal administration of 8-azaguanine, a purine antagonist, giving rise to non-sense or non-functional RNA within cell, significantly destroyed rat's ability to learn a new maze without impairing its ability to recall the already established or stored memory. Flexner and co-workers⁶ made a similar approach after intercerebral injection of puromycin, a well-known inhibitor of nucleic acid and protein synthesis, to experimental rats. It was found that depending upon the area of injection, a loss of short-term and long-term memory was found to take place. Results of all these experiments indicate that complicated metabolic changes may in some way be related with the structural changes of RNA constituents of the nerve cell bodies during increased neuronal activity, although it is too early to assess the physiological significance of net decrease or increase in the total protein or RNA neuronal or glial cells.

Most of the cytoplasmic ribonucleoproteins of nerve tissue is located in the Nissl bodies, although nuclei and nucleolar regions of nerve cells contain a significant amount of nucleoproteins. A normal, resting nerve cell gives a characteristic picture with basic dyes like gallocyanin-chromalum, thionine etc. or with ultraviolet microphotography. The characteristic histological picture of nerve cell, however, exhibits marked changes with variations in the functional and/or pathological activity of the cell. The most significant of these changes are alterations in the affinity for basic dyes, quantitative and qualitative changes in the distribution pattern of cytoplasmic ribonucleoproteins as well as alterations in the

3. Hyden, (1962) in *Macromolecular specificity and Biological Memory*. Ed. by F. O. Schmitt (MIT Press) Mass., p. 63.
4. A. Geiger, (1957) in *Metabolism of Nervous system*. Ed. by D. Richter (Pergamon Press) London, p. 249.
5. W. Dingman and M. B. Sporn, *J. Psychiat. Res.*, 1961, 1, 1.
6. J. B. Flexner, L. B. Flexner and E. Stellar, *Science*, 1963, 141, 57.

size and staining capacity of the nucleus, nucleolus and nuclear membrane^{7,8}. The chromatolytic type of cycle which these cytoplasmic and the nuclear ribonucleoprotein particles undergo during stimulation stress or drug action, has focussed attention on the properties and other characteristics of cytoplasmic and nuclear ribonucleoproteins of nerve tissue.

Many investigators have reported quantitative changes in either protein or RNA content of the nerve cell during chromatolysis⁹. Gersh and Bodian¹⁰ suggested that dissolution of Nissl granules during stress or stimulation of nerve cells may be due to the degradation of RNA into acid-soluble nucleotides. Bodian *et al*¹¹ reported that during chromatolysis, acid phosphatase activity increases in proportion to the degree of nucleoprotein breakdown. Ghosh and co-workers¹², Datta and Ghosh¹³, on the other hand, suggested that decreased stability of the cytoplasmic ribonucleoproteins may be associated with drug-induced chromatolytic changes in nerve cell. In contrast to these observations, the findings of Cohen¹⁴ and Gramp and Edström¹⁵ indicate that there need not be any quantitative changes in either the protein or RNA content of the nerve cell during chromatolysis.

Another interesting aspect of the chromatolytic phenomena, is that the increased chromatolysis of cytoplasmic ribonucleoproteins (as indicated by marked chromophobia), is generally accompanied by increased chromophilia of nucleolar regions and nuclear membranes (as revealed by deep staining). A possible explanation, as suggested by Bratigård, Edström and Hydén¹⁶ and Vraa-Jensen¹⁷, is that during increased functional activity, nucleolar and part of the nuclear regions pass through an active metabolic phase, giving rise to continual formation of new RNA molecules which exceed consumption and as a result this region exhibits chromophilic response. In the cytoplasmic regions on the other hand, due to continued functional activity, the consumption and breakdown of ribonucleoproteins or RNA constituents exceed synthesis and hence the net effect is observed in the form of chromatolysis. It seems that functional impairment of brain is related to some aspects of altered nucleoprotein metabolism as a result of which the cytoplasmic RNA or ribonucleoprotein constituents are used up followed by a tendency towards the exchange or release of RNA from the nucleolar regions.

7. L. Einarson, *J. Comp. Neurol.*, 1935, **61**, 101.
8. L. Einarson, *Acta Jullandica*, 1945, **17**, 1.
9. C. A. Hamberger and H. Hydén, *Acta Otolaryng (Stockh) Supp.*, 1949, **75**, 82.
10. J. Gersh and D. Bodian, *J. Cell. Comp. Physiol.*, 1943, **21**, 253.
11. D. Bodian and R. Mellors, *J. Exp. Med.*, 1945, **81**, 469.
12. J. J. Ghosh, R. K. Datta and K. C. Bhattacharyya, *Can. J. Biochem.*, 1965, **43**, 959.
13. R. K. Datta and J. J. Ghosh, *J. Neurochem.*, 1964, **11**, 595.
14. M. M. Cohen, *J. Neurochem.*, 1962, **8**, 337.
15. W. Gramp and J. E. Edström, *J. Neurochem.*, 1963, **10**, 725.
16. S. Bratigård, J. E. Edström and H. Hydén. (1957) in *The Metabolism of the Nervous System*. Ed. by D. Richter. (Pergamon Press), p. 425.
17. Vraa-Jensen, G. (1957) in *The Metabolism of the Nervous System*. Ed. by D. Richter. (Pergamon Press), p. 422.

Whether there is any relationship between the nucleo-cytoplasmic exchange of ribonucleic acid and the action of different neuropharmacologic drugs at the level of functional activity of nerve is still a matter for further speculation.

Characteristics of gallocyunin-chromalum stained tissue sections from nerve cell bodies of drug-treated rats : Figures 1-6 show the gallocyunin-chromalum stained sections of the spinal cord and hypothalamo-thalamo regions of normal and drug-treated rats. From the nature of the staining, it is evident that in the control section (Fig. 1) the Nissl granules give a characteristic dense, closely packed appearance

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

with deep staining, whereas the corresponding sections (Figs. 2-6), isolated from drug-treated rats, reveal that the Nissl granules are very faintly stained with granular appearances, indicating partial chromatolysis. In contrast to Nissl granules, nucleolar regions and nuclear membranes are intensely stained in tissue sections from

drug-treated rats in comparison to those of normal rats. Einarson¹⁸ also noted a similar increase in staining of nucleolus and nuclear membrane after cutting the axon. According to Einarson, this may indicate the passage of basophilic materials from nucleolar and nuclear regions to the cytoplasm. The basophilic interchange between nuclear regions and cytoplasm during chromatolysis is also supported by Gersh and Bodian¹⁹ and Hydén¹⁹.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

Table I contains the results of the endogenous release of acid-soluble nucleotides from tissue sections of normal and drug-treated rats and shows that there is a significantly increased release from tissue sections of drug-treated animals. The release is very marked in the case of tissue sections from strychnine, picrotoxin and chlorpromazine treated animals.

18. L. Einarson, (1957) in *The Metabolism of the Nervous System*. Ed. by D. Richter, (Pergamon Press), p. 403.
19. H. Hydén, *Acta Physiol. Scand.*, 1943, 6, Suppl. 17.

The results of the histological and biochemical findings indicate that administration of different neuropharmacological drugs bring about striking changes in the Nissl granules and in other structural constituents of the nerve cell bodies of rats. The dissolution of the Nissl granules may either be due to the changes in the affinity for gallocyanin chromalum staining or to quantitative changes in the ribonucleic acid content of the granules. It is possible that during the action of different neuropharmacologic drugs, perhaps from metabolic stress associated with other functional disturbances, a rapid intracellular turnover of proteins and nucleic acids takes place in neuronal cytoplasm, as a result of which cytoplasmic

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6.

ribonucleoprotein may undergo alterations at the structural level. Increased release of acid-soluble nucleotides from drug-treated tissue sections (Table I) on the other hand supports the assumption that nucleic acid constituent may undergo quantitative changes under the experimental conditions studied. The significant increase in both nucleolar and nucleolar sizes may indicate that during the action of neuropharmacologic drugs, both nucleolar and nuclear regions pass through

an active metabolic phase, giving rise to continual formation of new RNA molecules which are redistributed in the cytoplasmic regions. It seems that during the action of different neuropharmacologic drugs, the functional activity of the nerve is altered in such a way that cytoplasmic RNA or ribonucleoproteins are used up, followed by a tendency towards the exchange or release of RNA from the nucleolar regions.

TABLE I
Endogenous release of acid-soluble nucleotides from normal and drug-treated spinal cord tissue sections.

Group	Dose and Time of killing	Acid-soluble nucleotides released*
Normal (saline treated)	—	50 ± 2
Strychnine treated	5 mg. kg. (16-18 min.)	123 ± 3
Picrotoxin treated	10 mg. kg. (20-25 min.)	105 ± 5
Chlorpromazine treated	250 mg. kg. (180 min.)	138 ± 4
Chlordiazepoxide (Librium) treated	50 mg. kg. (60 min.)	95 ± 5

* Each value, represents the mean of six different experiments ± S.E.

TABLE II
Chemical composition of Brain cortex Ribosomes isolated from Drug-treated Rats.
(Values expressed as mg./100 mg. ribosomes)

Source and nature of Ribosomes	Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Protein	RNA
<i>Normal (Saline treated)</i>				
Cytoplasmic	12.8 ± 0.6	3.8 ± 0.3	64.3 ± 1.2	35.7 ± 0.8
Nuclear	12.1 ± 0.6	4.1 ± 0.4	60.2 ± 1.5	39.8 ± 0.9
<i>Chlorpromazine treated (50 mg/kg.)</i>				
Cytoplasmic	12.5 ± 0.8	4.8 ± 0.5	60.1 ± 0.8	39.9 ± 0.7
Nuclear	12.3 ± 0.7	4.4 ± 0.8	60.8 ± 1.2	39.2 ± 0.6
<i>Prochlorperazine treated (10 mg/kg.)</i>				
Cytoplasmic	12.3 ± 0.7	3.2 ± 0.7	64.2 ± 0.7	35.8 ± 0.8
Nuclear	12.9 ± 0.8	4.8 ± 0.5	60.1 ± 0.8	39.9 ± 0.7
<i>Strychnine treated (5 mg/kg.)</i>				
Cytoplasmic	13.2 ± 0.7	3.4 ± 0.4	65.2 ± 0.6	34.8 ± 0.7
Nuclear	12.5 ± 0.9	4.6 ± 0.6	59.7 ± 0.8	40.3 ± 0.8
<i>Picrotoxin treated (10 mg/kg.)</i>				
Cytoplasmic	12.8 ± 0.5	3.7 ± 0.5	64.5 ± 0.7	35.5 ± 0.6
Nuclear	12.2 ± 0.8	4.5 ± 0.7	60.5 ± 0.8	39.5 ± 0.5

Mean of the analyses of ten different preparation ± S.D.

Studies on Cytoplasmic Ribonucleoproteins : In order to understand the drug-induced changes in the ribonucleoprotein constituents of brain tissue, further studies have been carried out on the cytoplasmic ribosomal fractions, isolated by conventional procedure, from the brain tissues of drug-treated rats. Studies have been made on the changes in the chemical constituents, enzymic activity and on the stability and related properties of the ribosomal particles from brain cortex tissues of normal and drug-treated rats.

Effect of Drug treatment in the chemical composition of Brain Cortex Ribosomes : In order to find whether the administration of different neuropharmacologic drugs cause any change in the major chemical component of the brain cortex ribosomes, studies were made on the chemical composition of both cytoplasmic and nuclear ribosomal particles isolated from chlorpromazine, prochlorperazine, strychnine sulphate and picrotoxin sulphate treated rat brain. Table II presents the chemical composition of the brain cortex ribosomal particles isolated from the drug treated rats.

Results (Table II) indicate that the drug treatment did not cause significant changes in the major chemical component of the ribosomes.

Effect of Drug Treatment on the Ultraviolet Absorption Spectrum Characteristics of Brain Cortex Ribosomes : Figures 7 and 8 show the U.V. absorption spectra of cytoplasmic and nuclear ribosomes, isolated from the brain cortex tissues

FIG. 7.

FIG. 8.

of different drug-treated rats. From both the figures it will be evident that there are no significant differences between the pattern of the U.V. absorption spectra of cytoplasmic and nuclear ribosomes of the brain cortex tissues of drug-treated rats and those of normal rats.

Effect of Drug Treatment on the Nucleotide Composition of Brain Cortex Ribosomal RNA : As no significant changes were observed in the chemical composition of brain cortex ribosomes from drug-treated rats, further studies were carried out to find out changes, if any, in the nucleotide composition of the ribosomal RNA isolated from brain cortex tissues of drug-treated rats. Table III presents the data of the nucleotide composition of the RNA isolated from different ribosomes. Results indicate that drug treatment did not cause significant change in the nucleotide composition of the ribosomal RNA.

TABLE III
Nucleotide Composition of Ribosomes from the Brain Cortex Tissues.

Source of Ribosomes	Adenylic acid moles,100	Cytidylic acid moles of nucleotides	Guanylic acid	Uridylic acid
<i>Normal</i> Cytoplasmic ribosomes	21.7 ± 0.6	30.1 ± 0.6	32.8 ± 0.8	15.4 ± 0.8
Nuclear ribosomes	20.4 ± 0.5	30.2 ± 1.1	28.1 ± 0.7	21.3 ± 1.1
<i>Chlorpromazine treated</i> Cytoplasmic ribosomes	20.5 ± 0.7	31.5 ± 0.9	30.8 ± 0.8	17.2 ± 0.6
Nuclear ribosomes	19.6 ± 0.5	32.4 ± 0.5	26.5 ± 0.6	21.5 ± 0.7
<i>Prochlorperazine treated</i> Cytoplasmic ribosomes	20.8 ± 0.8	29.5 ± 0.6	31.5 ± 0.8	18.2 ± 0.7
Nuclear ribosomes	20.5 ± 0.7	31.6 ± 1.2	28.8 ± 0.7	19.1 ± 0.8
<i>Strychnine treated</i> Cytoplasmic ribosomes	22.0 ± 1.0	30.8 ± 1.0	32.8 ± 1.3	14.4 ± 0.7
Nuclear ribosomes	21.5 ± 0.9	28.6 ± 1.0	31.6 ± 1.2	18.3 ± 0.8
<i>Picrotoxin treated</i> Cytoplasmic ribosomes	22.6 ± 0.9	30.4 ± 1.1	32.6 ± 1.2	14.4 ± 0.6
Nuclear ribosomes	20.5 ± 0.7	29.2 ± 0.5	30.8 ± 0.7	18.6 ± 0.3

Mean of the analyses of ten different preparations ± S.D.

Studies on the stability of Brain Cortex Ribosomes from Drug-treated Rats : The chromatolysis of Nissl granules may to some extent be associated with the decreased stability of these particles. Hence, the stability of the ribosomes isolated from the brain of drug-treated animals was studied to understand the observed chromatolysis. Kihara *et al.*²⁰ studied the stability of 80 S yeast cells

on the basis of the release of various components in different media. An approach was made in the present investigation to determine the state of stability of the ribosomes as induced by drug treatment, by following the rate of degradation in some suitable suspension media. The choice of the different suspension media was made on the basis that the stability of ribosomal particles is affected by high salt concentration²¹, urea²⁰, phosphate²⁰, EDTA²² etc. In the present study the relative stability of the ribosomal particles from drug-treated slices was measured in terms of the release of protein, RNA, and acid-soluble nucleotides in the suspension media containing these different constituents. Gilchrist and Bock²³ observed that ribonucleoprotein particles remained more stable in 0.005 M magnesium cacodylate buffer, pH 7.0. In the present study magnesium cacodylate buffer of the same molarity and pH was used as a suitable control medium for suspension of ribosomes. Table IV summarized the results of studies concerned with the release of protein, RNA, and acid-soluble nucleotide components from the ribosomes of drug-treated slices into different media.

TABLE IV

Stability of Cytoplasmic Ribosomes from Brain Cortex Tissues of Drug-treated Rats.

25 mg. portions of cytoplasmic ribosomes, containing 16.1 mg. protein and 8.9 mg. RNA were suspended in 5 ml. of 0.005M Mg. cacodylate buffer, pH, 7.0, in which agents indicated in the table were dissolved with adjustment of pH wherever necessary. After incubation at 37°C for 3 hr. the mixture was centrifuged at 105,000 for 1 hr. The supernatants were used for the estimation of proteins, RNA and acid soluble nucleotides. The concentration of acid-soluble nucleotides was determined on the basis of optical density value of 33 at 260 mμ of a solution containing 1 mg. equivalent of nucleotide mixture obtained from complete hydrolysis of 1 mg. yeast RNA.

Source of cytoplasmic Ribosomes	Released components studied	Amounts (mg./5 ml.) released in 3 hr. in suspension media of*			
		Controls (in 0.005 M Mg-cacodylate, pH 7.0)	Mg Cl ₂ 0.01 M	EDTA 0.01 M	Phosphate 0.05 M
Untreated (saline control)	Protein	0.32 ± 0.03	0.44 ± 0.04	0.60 ± 0.04	0.65 ± 0.05
	RNA	0.15 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.03	0.28 ± 0.03
	Acid-soluble nucleotides	0.02 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01
Chlorpromazine treated (50 mg/kg.)	Protein	0.82 ± 0.06	0.85 ± 0.10	1.10 ± 0.10	1.18 ± 0.08
	RNA	0.52 ± 0.04	0.48 ± 0.05	0.78 ± 0.07	0.87 ± 0.06
	Acid-soluble nucleotides	0.08 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.01
Strychnine treated (5 mg/kg.)	Protein	0.98 ± 0.10	0.95 ± 0.12	1.25 ± 0.15	1.20 ± 0.12
	RNA	0.63 ± 0.08	0.54 ± 0.10	0.84 ± 0.08	0.92 ± 0.10
	Acid-soluble nucleotides	0.12 ± 0.05	0.09 ± 0.05	0.28 ± 0.03	0.32 ± 0.05

* Mean of seven different experiments ± S.E.M.

21. K. McQuillen, in *Protein Biosynthesis*, (1961), Acad. Press, p. 280.
22. F. C. Chao and H. K. Schachman, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1956, **61**, 220.
23. W. C. Gilchrist and R. M. Bock. In *Microsomal Particles and Protein Biosynthesis*, (Pergamon Press), p. 1.

TABLE V

Stability of Nuclear Ribosomes from Brain Cortex Tissues of Drug-treated Rats.

25 mg. portions of nuclear ribosomes containing 15.1 mg. protein and 9.9 mg. RNA were suspended in 0.005 M Mg-cacodylate buffer, pH 7.0, the other conditions used were same as in Table IV.

Source of nuclear Ribosomes	Released components studied	Amounts (mg/5 ml.) released in 3 hr. in suspension media of*			
		Controls (in 0.005 M Mg cacodylate, pH 7.0)	Mg Cl ₂ 0.01 M	EDTA 0.01 M	Phosphate 0.05 M
Untreated (saline control)	Protein	0.30 ± 0.07	0.45 ± 0.05	0.60 ± 0.07	0.65 ± 0.08
	RNA	0.12 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.03	0.28 ± 0.03
	Acid-soluble nucleotides	0.04 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01
Chlorpromazine treated (50 mg/kg.)	Protein	0.48 ± 0.05	0.58 ± 0.07	0.70 ± 0.09	0.78 ± 0.07
	RNA	0.22 ± 0.03	0.31 ± 0.04	0.52 ± 0.04	0.55 ± 0.05
	Acid-soluble nucleotides	0.04 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.02
Strychnine treated (5 mg/kg.)	Protein	0.40 ± 0.05	0.50 ± 0.04	0.72 ± 0.08	0.75 ± 0.08
	RNA	0.20 ± 0.05	0.32 ± 0.05	0.50 ± 0.05	0.58 ± 0.05
	Acid-soluble nucleotides	0.06 ± 0.02	0.05 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.02

* Mean of seven different experiments ± S.E.M.

Results (Tables IV and V) show that ribosomes isolated from drug-treated brain cortex slices became more susceptible to breakdown, as revealed by the increased release of protein, RNA, and acid-soluble nucleotides in different media. A general idea about the degree of stability of the different ribosomal particles may be formed from the results obtained after they were suspended in magnesium cacodylate buffer, or in the presence of EDTA. It is observed that in these suspension media greater release of proteins, total RNA, and acid-soluble nucleotides takes place from the ribosomes of drug-treated tissue. In the presence of phosphate there is a greater tendency for the release of protein components from the ribosomes of drug-treated tissue than there is in the control. In the presence of magnesium chloride, the release of different components from ribosomes, obtained either from normal or drug-treated tissues, is not much different. These results further indicate that in intact tissue these drugs act either directly or indirectly by affecting the different factors needed for the stability of ribosomal structure. The induction of instability in the ribosomal particles with consequent loss of enzymic activities, which was previously observed by Datta and Ghosh²⁴ may probably be a mechanism of action of these drugs at the cellular level.

Studies on the Ribosomal RNA from the Brain Cortex Tissues of Drug-treated Rats: Although attempts have been made to interpret the loss of stability of ribosomal particles in terms of breakdown of nucleic acids and proteins, no studies have been made to determine the mechanism involved in the loss of the stability or structural integrity of the brain cortex ribosomes under drug-treated conditions. Since the secondary structure plays an important role in maintaining the stability or integrity of both RNA and protein, an approach has been made in the present investigation to a study of the mechanism of disorganization of the brain cortex ribosomes, isolated from chlorpromazine and strychnine treated rats, mainly from the stand point of the intramolecular organization of RNA within the compact conformation of the ribosome itself.

TABLE VI

Thermal Hyperchromicity and Degree of Hydrogen bonded structure of Ribosomal RNA preparations.

Source of Ribosomal RNA	% Thermal hyperchromicity* (at 260 m μ , between 30 and 85°C)	% Hydrogen-bonded structure (that of normal RNA taken as 100)
<i>Cytoplasmic Ribosomal RNA</i> Normal (untreated)	12.9 $\pm$ 0.8	100
Chlorpromazine (50 mg/kg.)	8.0 $\pm$ 1.0	63
Strychnine sulphate (5 mg/kg.)	8.5 $\pm$ 0.7	66
<i>Nuclear Ribosomal RNA</i> Normal (untreated)	14.8 $\pm$ 0.7	100
Chlorpromazine (50 mg/kg.)	14.5 $\pm$ 1.2	97
Strychnine sulphate (5 mg/kg.)	14.0 $\pm$ 0.8	94

* Mean values of determinations using six different RNA preparations $\pm$ S.E.M.

Further investigations in the changes, if any, in the secondary structure of the ribosomal RNA due to drug treatment, was carried out by absorbancy-temperature profile measurements and the results are expressed in terms of percentage thermal hyperchromicity and percentage hydrogen-bonded structure retained (Table VI). It is evident from Table VI that the ribosomal RNA of normal, untreated rat brain, shows a greater thermal hyperchromicity, while the ribosomal RNA's from drug-treated rat brain show lower thermal hyperchromicity in the corresponding temperature range. The lower thermal hyperchromic effect in the case of ribosomal RNA's from drug-treated brain tissues are indicative of the loss of organized structure of RNA in these particles.

DISCUSSION

Systematic studies have been carried out, in the present investigation, to understand the role of different non-enzymic factors that are involved in the neuropharmacologic drug induced changes in the cytoplasmic ribonucleoprotein constituents of brain tissue, as has been observed histologically by using gallo-cyanin-chromalum staining method. Although no marked changes have been observed at the level of chemical and nucleotide compositions and the ultraviolet absorption characteristics of cytoplasmic and nuclear ribosomes from the brain cortex tissues of normal and drug-treated rats, significant changes in the stability characteristics of cytoplasmic ribosomes from the brain cortex of drug-treated rats have been observed. The stability of nuclear ribosomes, under the same conditions, has not been shown to be affected.

Although little precise data are available about the different factors affecting the stability of native macromolecular structure of ribonucleoproteins, the few established results indicate that the combination of RNA with ribosomal protein in ribosomes does not disturb the macromolecular organization of RNA^{25,26}. Protein component, on the other hand, helps to maintain effectively the stability of RNA conformations within the ribosomal structure by regulating the equilibrium between different intramolecular forces, mostly between the forces of hydrogen bonding and electrostatic repulsion. According to Spirin²⁷, the stability of RNA within the integrated structure of ribosomes is maintained to a great extent by 'the equilibrium between the two opposing forces that determines the degree of chain coiling, spatial asymmetry of the macromolecule and the degree of its compactness'. Factor or factors which affect the forces of hydrogen bonding or electrostatic repulsion in one way or the other, will not only influence the secondary structure of RNA but also the overall stability of the ribonucleoprotein structure. The presence of basic proteins, bivalent cations like Mg⁺⁺, polyamines etc. are known to stabilize the ribonucleoprotein structure by sufficient shielding of negatively charged phosphate groups so that the forces of hydrogen bonding exceed the effective electrostatic repulsion, resulting in compact conformations with more stable helical regions. If the electrostatic repulsion at the site of negatively charged phosphate groups of RNA exceeds the intramolecular

25. D. Schlessinger, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1960, 2, 92.

26. G. Zubay and M. H. F. Wilkins, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1960, 2, 105.

27. A. S. Spirin, (1963) In *Progress in Nucleic Acid Research*. Ed. by J. N. Davidson and W. E. Cohn, Vol. I (Acad. Press), p. 301.

hydrogen bonding forces, then the helical regions in the RNA structure become more unstable resulting in the decreased stability of ribonucleoproteins. The latter condition may develop due to the following causes :

(a) Deficiency or displacement of magnesium from the binding sites of ribosome which may arise as a result of

- (i) low counter-ion concentration of Mg^{++} ;
 - (ii) increase of Na^+ ion concentration which is more effective than K^+ ion in the displacement of Mg^{++} ;
 - (iii) increase of phosphate ions.
- (b) Decrease of ionic strength of the solution.
- (c) Breaking or weakening of hydrogen bonding forces by urea or formamide.
- (d) Dissociation of protein component from the RNA moiety.
- (e) Deficiency of polyamines or other basic compound.

In the light of these discussions on the mechanisms controlling ribosomal stability, it may be concluded from the present study that drug induced instability of the cytoplasmic ribosomal particles or rat brain cortex tissues may arise as a result of the disturbances in the equilibrium between electrostatic repulsion and hydrogen bonding forces and most plausibly the electrostatic repulsion exceeding the hydrogen bonding forces. The whole process may be initiated or triggered either through the displacement of magnesium or other positively charged materials such as polyamines, basic proteins etc., the details of which have already been discussed. The net result is that the intra-chain hydrogen bonds in RNA are weakened and the secondary structure of ribosomal RNA is destroyed. Finally, the RNA moiety becomes more susceptible to enzymic attack by RNase, although this degradation of ribosomal RNA remains greatly hindered so long as the compact, secondary structure of RNA remains intact (Elson²⁸). Ohtaka and Uchida²⁹ found in the case of yeast ribosomes, that 'the stability of ribosome depends on the intactness of RNA rather than on the activation of latent RNase'.

Results emerging from this study indicate that hydrogen bonded structures of the cytoplasmic ribosomal RNA's from the brain cortex of rats treated with different neuropharmacologic drugs, are destroyed to a significant extent in comparison to those of untreated control. The impaired stability of brain cortex cytoplasmic ribonucleoprotein constituents in drug-treated animals may be explained on the basis of this finding. On the other hand, the hydrogen bonded structures of the brain cortex nuclear ribosomal RNA's from the different drug-treated rats are not appreciably altered in comparison to those observed with

28. D. Elson, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta.*, 1959, **36**, 372.

29. Y. Ohtaka and K. Uchida, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta.*, 1963, **78**, 94.

untreated control. This may explain the relative insensitivity of nuclear ribosomes, towards disorganization as a result of drug treatment. It is also reasonable to conclude further that the factor or factors viz., deficiency or displacement of Mg^{++} ions, polyamines, H-bond weakening agents, etc. which are responsible for bringing about the 'denaturation' of the secondary structure of ribosomal RNA, are not possibly present in the 'milieu' surrounding the nuclear ribosomes or the other alternative is that even if these factors be present, they are not active due to some unknown reasons. The localized or selective distribution of metabolites or cellular constituents, surrounding the cytoplasmic or nuclear ribosomal particles, is not difficult to conceive in view of the idea of compartmentalization of metabolic events at the subcellular level, as suggested by Waelsch³⁰. In fact, the inter-relationship between the structural as well as the functional changes of ribosomes and the selective distribution of different cellular constituents which are known to affect the ribosomal stability, is a particularly promising area for further investigation, which would certainly contribute to a better understanding of the action of different neuropharmacologic drugs at the sub-cellular or even at the molecular level.

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30. H. Waelsch, Fourth Int. Cong. Biochem. (Vienna), 1961, 3, 36.